

Preparation and Molecular Weights of Higher Alkoxides of Aluminum*

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Preparation of Aluminum tert.-alkoxides and their corresponding mixed mono-isopropoxide di-tert.-alkoxides by alcohol interchange between aluminum isopropoxide and the appropriate tert.-alcohol is successfully carried out. Starting from tert.-butoxide the higher alkoxides are prepared even more suitably by the interchange method. The preparation of mono-isopropoxide di-tert.-butoxide was standardized. The molecular weights of these newly prepared compounds were determined ebullioscopically, in benzene and toluene.

ALCOHOL interchange was mentioned by Tischenko¹ and Adkins and Cox². It was applied by Mehrotra^{3,4} in preparing normal and secondary alkoxides of aluminum by interchanging the appropriate alcohol with aluminum isopropoxide, for studying their physico-chemical properties. However it was reported that aluminum tert.-butoxide and aluminum tert.-amyloxide could not be prepared by this method. It was suggested that steric hindrance due to bulky tert.-butoxide and tert.-amyloxide groups prevented interchange of the third isopropoxide group with tert.-alkoxide group from the tert.-alcohol. The following structures were proposed with the isopropoxide group being in the bridging positions:

In a brief note⁵ Bains reported the successful preparation of aluminum tert.-butoxide, aluminum tert.-amyloxide and di-ethyl, methyl carbinoloxide by interchange method. This work has now been extended to the preparation of aluminum triethyl carbinoloxide. Starting from aluminum tert.-butoxide

a more easy and elegant method for preparing higher tert.-alkoxides is reported. Preparation of mixed alkoxides of these higher alkoxides is described. The determination of molecular weights carried out to find the degree of polymerization (or association) among these alkoxides and mixed alkoxides is reported for the first time.

Experimental

Carefully cleaned apparatus was given a rinsing with dilute alkali solution followed by thorough washing with distilled water prior to drying. This was to destroy any trace of an acid which may hydrolyse or catalyse the decomposition of the aluminum compounds being prepared. Rigorous precautions were also taken to avoid any hydrolysis due to moisture from the air. Experiments were carried out under dry nitrogen atmosphere.

Alcohols were treated with small amounts of sodium metal to destroy any acid impurities and distilled. Following this treatment, tert.-butanol was dehydrated and purified azeotropically in the presence of ethanol and benzene, the latter being in large excess. Other alcohols were also dried in the same manner. Benzene was not removed entirely; anhydrous mixtures of alcohols with benzene were used as such. Analar grade benzene and toluene were dried azeotropically after keeping over potassium hydroxide pallets overnight to remove any traces of acidic impurities.

Aluminum isopropoxide was prepared by a reported method⁶. The product was purified by multiple distillation under reduced pressure.

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Analysis :

Aluminum was precipitated and weighed as oxinate. An oxidation method was used for the determination of isopropoxide⁷, where possible.

Preparation of Aluminum tert.-Alkoxides :

Below is described the preparation of aluminum tert.-alkoxides. The preparation of aluminum tert.-butoxide and tert.-amyloxide is given in greater detail followed by simple outlines in the case of other ones ; some results are given in the form of a table.

Aluminum tert.-butoxide :

To a solution of aluminum iso-propoxide (14.4 g) in anhydrous benzene (100 ml) was added tert.-butanol (60 g). This solution was refluxed for 48 hours during which time the binary azeotrope was removed from time to time at 72-74°. The main bulk of the azeotrope was removed slowly during the last 10 hours. In all about three quarters of benzene and alcohol was thus distilled off. After cooling the volatile contents were removed under reduced pressure. The product weighed 18.2 g. The results of analysis corresponded approximately to the empirical composition of $\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^t)_2(\text{OBu}^t)_2$, the ratio of aluminum to isopropoxide being 3.

Found : Al, 10.85, 11.00 , OPr^t , 7.50, 7.60%

Calculated for composition above : Al, 11.18, OPr^t , 8.15.

The above product (8.4 g) was again refluxed with an excess of tert.-butanol-benzene azeotrope (200 ml) for twenty five hours. The alcohol-benzene azeotrope was collected and the main solvent content was refluxed off in the last 2-3 hours. The liquid content of the cooled solution was removed by distillation under vacuum.

Found : Al, 11.29, 11.33 ; OPr^t , 2.15, 2.55%.

This product was sublimed and its analysis corresponded to the completely substituted alkoxide.

Found : Al, 10.91, 10.90 ; OPr^t <1%
 $\text{Al}(\text{OBu}^t)_3$ requires ; Al, 10.95

The results given above are typical for a few more experimental runs with slight variations in the conditions regarding time of refluxing and the proportions of the reagents used.

Aluminum tert.-amyloxide :

To a solution of aluminum isopropoxide (12.5 g) in benzene (150 ml) was added a solution of 55 g. of 87% tert.-amyl alcohol in benzene. First the benzene-isopropanol azeotrope was taken out at 72°. After 10 hours refluxing, the distillate was occasionally run off until the temperature reached 78°, when the solvent was steadily removed until temperature of boiling benzene was approached. On refluxing it for

another 12 hours there was a drop of only a degree in the temperature in the reflux column. Most of the solvent was then distilled off until only about 60 ml of the solution was left. After cooling tert.-amyl alcohol was evaporated first at room temperature with a low vacuum followed by warming under high vacuum for about two hours. The product which weighed about 18 g, gave the following analytical results*

Found : Al, 9.51, 9.50 ; Apparent OPr^t , 9.02, 8.56%.

This product was sublimed at 130-135° bath temperature under 0.02-0.03 mm Hg pressure.

Found : Al, 9.29, 9.35%.

$\text{Al}(\text{OAm}^t)_3$ requires : Al, 9.37%

Aluminum di-ethyl, methyl carbinoloxide :

Aluminum isopropoxide (5.0 g), and di-ethyl, methyl carbinol (15.0 g) were refluxed in benzene (80 ml) for half an hour. Most of the solvent was removed and it was again allowed to be refluxed with a fresh lot of the solvent (50 ml) overnight. The total reflux time was 30 hours. The volatiles were removed under vacuum. A thick gluey product was obtained. Yield was 8.1 g.

In an effort to crystallize, this product was dissolved in ether solvate (25 ml). The product was then evacuated to remove the solvent. The product remained gluey. It was again evacuated for half an hour at 70°, without any change in the appearance of the product.

Found : Al, 8.29, 8.40% ; $\text{Al}(\text{OCMeEt}_2)_3$ requires : Al 8.18%.

The product was sublimed at 110-115° bath temperature under 10^{-3} mm Hg pressure with a slight change in the content of aluminum.

Found : Al, 8.24, 8.25%.

Aluminum tri-ethyl carbinoloxide :

To aluminum isopropoxide (9 g), tri-ethyl carbinol (120 ml of 18% in benzene) was added and the mixture refluxed for two days at 130° bath temperature using a small column. The azeotrope was removed from time to time during this period. The volatiles were sucked off after cooling the contents. The product left was a thick liquid.

* To check any isopropoxide moiety in the above product a sample of the product having tert.-amyl alcohol and a blank with the same amount of pure tert.-amyl alcohol were reacted with chromic acid solution under identical conditions⁷. The apparent isopropoxide content in both cases was found to be the same confirming thereby that the alkoxide prepared does not have any significant- OPr^t moiety in it. The apparent content of reducing moiety is determined because unlike tert.-butanol, tert.-amyl alcohol reacts, though slowly, with chromic solution.

Found : Al, 9.00, 9.03% ; Al(OPr^t)_{1.5}(OCET₃)_{1.5}, requires : Al, 8.95%.

The liquid on distillation at 190-195° gave the same aluminum content.

In another run the liquid product obtained was subjected to high vacuum at 50° for 4-5 hours. A highly viscous product was obtained which analysed : Found : Al, 8.73, 8.72% ; Al(OPr^t)₂(OCET₃)₂ requires : Al, 8.54%.

The combined product of the above experiments was treated with ~ 50 g of the alcohol in 100 ml benzene. The contents were refluxed for 12 hours as mildly as possible and the azeotrope was removed from time to time. On evacuating the volatile contents of the above reaction mixture at 75°, the product left was a thick liquid which on cooling became glassy.

Found : Al, 7.35, 7.28% , Al(OCET₃)₃ requires : Al, 7.26%.

Reactions between Aluminum tert.-butoxide and tert.-carbinols :

Aluminum tert.-butoxide (8.0 g) in anhydrous benzene (200 ml) and an excess (1 : 5 moles) of the respective tert.-carbinol was added. The reaction contents were brought to a gentle boil using a small column (12") packed with Fenske helices and provided with a column head. The alcohol-benzene azeotrope was distilled off. Then the product was kept under near boiling conditions for a few hours and again the azeotrope (if any) was distilled off along with excess solvent. Finally the volatile contents were removed first at room temperature and then at 75°. A portion of the gluey product was sublimed. The results of analysis are included in table 1, a.

Preparation of Mixed Aluminum tert.-alkoxides :

The preparation of aluminum mono-isopropoxide di-tert -butoxide will be described in some detail and will be applied to the preparation of other mixed alkoxides of higher tert.-alcohols. The analytical results will be presented in the form of a table.

Aluminum mono-isopropoxide, di-tert.-butoxide :

A weighed amount of aluminum tert-butoxide prepared by the alcohol interchange method described above was taken in a two necked flask (150 ml) containing benzene (70 g). Isopropanol (5% in excess) was taken in a small funnel and was diluted with benzene(30 ml). It was added to the solution of aluminum tert-butoxide under reflux ; slow addition was adopted to avoid uneven replacement of the tert.-butoxide groups. After addition the reaction solution was refluxed overnight. On cooling the solvent was evaporated off under vacuum.

After complete removal of the solvent, the product was analysed for isopropoxide content and in case it was more than 26% the material was refluxed with some tert. butanol in benzene solution for some time (say 1-2 hours). If the isopropoxide content was 25-26% the material was regarded satisfactory and was sublimed to be followed by another elemental analysis. Some of the results are given below :

Found : Al, 11.68, 11.63% ; OPr^t, 25.96, 25.75% for experiment I
Al, 11.55, 11.58% , OPr^t, 25.00, 25.05% for experiment II
Al, 11.65, 11.60% , OPr^t, 25.40, 25.25% for experiment III

Al(OPr^t)(OBu^t)₂ requires : Al, 11.61% , OPr^t, 25.45%.

The even distribution of the isopropoxide groups, was tested by molecular weight determination and from the nuclear magnetic resonance spectrum⁴. If the distribution was not even the molecular weight was found to be higher than required for a dimer and the nuclear magnetic resonance spectrum was more complex than expected for the mixed dimeric species.

Other Mixed Aluminum tert.-alkoxides :

Aluminum mono-isopropoxide, di-tert.-amyloxide, aluminum mono-isopropoxide bis-diethylmethyl carbinoloxide, and aluminum monoisopropoxide, bis-triethylcarbinoloxide, were prepared by the same method as that described for the preparation of active aluminum mono-isopropoxide, di-tert-butoxide. The analytical results are given in table 1, b.

TABLE 1.—CHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF THE PURE MIXED ALUMINUM ALKOXIDES.

Alkoxide	Percentage Aluminum	
	Found	Calculated
(a)		
Al(OCET ₃) ₃	7.20,7.30	7.26
Al(OCMeEt ₂) ₃	8.20,8.25	8.18
Al(OCMe ₂ Et) ₃	9.38,9.39	9.37
(b)		
Al(OPr ^t)(OMe ₂ Et) ₂	10.35,10.39	10.38
Al(OPr ^t)(OCMeEt ₂) ₂	9.29, 9.35	9.37
Al(OPr ^t)(OCET ₃) ₂	8.50, 8.51	8.54

Molecular Weight :

The molecular weights of the tert.-alkoxides and mixed tert -alkoxides were determined ebullioscopically in anhydrous benzene and anhydrous toluene using recrystallized fluorene for internal calibration. For each estimation 6-8 readings were taken over 0.02-0.30 molal concentration. Straight line graphs

were obtained. 2-3 experiments were carried out for each compound. The results are given in table 2.

could not be prepared at all. On the contrary the partial replacement of the third ethoxide group from

TABLE 2—MOLECULAR WEIGHTS OF ALUMINUM ALKOXIDES AND MIXED ALKOXIDES IN BOILING BENZENE AND TOLUENE*

Alkoxide	Benzene		Toluene	
	Molecular Weight	Complexity	Molecular Weight	Complexity
Al(OBu ^t) ₃	480.0*	1.95	465.0	1.89
Al(OPi ^t , (OBu ^t) ₂	460.0*	1.98	452.0	1.95
Al(OAm ^t) ₃	550.0	1.91	519.0	1.80
Al(OPi ^t , (OAm ^t) ₂	512.0*	1.97	494.0	1.90
Al(OCEt ₂ Me) ₃	607.0	1.84	530.0	1.61
Al(OPi ^t , (OCEt ₂ Me) ₂	—	—	533.0	1.85
Al(OCEt ₃) ₃	669.0	1.80	—	—
Al(OPi ^t , (OCEt ₃) ₂	609.0	1.93	489.0	1.55

* these values have been reported in literature (3¹⁴), but were redetermined and found to be the same. The reported values, instead of the new ones are included for comparison.

Discussion

Alcohol Interchange and Preparation of Alkoxides :

Alcohol interchange, during the last two decades, has made possible the preparation of a large number of alkoxides of the transition metals, which otherwise would present many difficulties, such as the side reaction, which leads to acid catalysed olefin formation and consequent hydrolysis in the preparation of tert-alkoxides. This difficulty was, to a large extent, overcome by the introduction of ammonia and pyridine in the reaction medium for the preparation of primary and secondary alkoxides⁸. An easily preparable primary or secondary alkoxide of the metal could thus be synthesized and interchange with a tert-alcohol brought about without any risk of hydrolysis and olefin formation, the medium being non-acidic. The higher alkoxides could, thus, be prepared, in pure form. The lower alcohol produced during the interchange could be removed azeotropically. There are two conditions, generally, applicable to the preparation of alkoxides which must be given special attention in case of high boiling tert-alkanols, which are more likely to be dehydrated and thus cause hydrolysis. These conditions are particularly applicable to the preparation of aluminum alkoxides :

- i. the reactants, the apparatus and the solvents, besides being well dried, should be free of all acidic impurities.
- ii. any overheating during refluxing should be avoided; heating mantles or any devices causing local overheating of the reaction flask may not be used. An oil bath is, indeed an ideal device recommended for refluxing. The minimum bath temperature compatible with a reasonable boil-up rate in the reflux column is desired.

As mentioned in the introduction, it has been reported that repeated attempts to prepare aluminum tert-alkoxides from aluminum isopropoxide had failed^{8, 4}. Aluminum tert-butoxide was obtained by a literature method⁸ but aluminum tert-amylxide

aluminum ethoxide by tert.-butanol was mentioned. A product of the empirical composition Al₂OEt(OBu^t)₅ was obtained by trans-esterification of aluminum ethoxide with tert-butyl acetate⁴. Further, Baker¹⁰ studied reactions of aluminum isopropoxide with esters successfully. From this information in the literature it is possible to discern that steric hindrance alone does not inhibit complete interchange ; it is most likely a contributory factor in slowing down the interchange reaction of smaller alkoxide groups with higher branched alcohols.

The preparation of aluminum tert.-butoxide and aluminum tert.-amylxide showed that whereas the latter compound was obtained in more or less one charge, more than one charge of tert.-butanol was required in the case of aluminum tert.-butoxide and the interchange had to be continued over a longer period of time. The +I inductive effect of the tert.-amyl group is slightly higher than that of the tert.-butyl group ; however the steric factor should remain the same. Moreover the binary azeotropes of isopropanol and tert.-butanol with benzene boil at a close range of temperature, with a little thermodynamic forward push for the interchange in question ; tert.-amyl alcohol solution boils at a higher temperature, effecting the interchange, seemingly at a faster rate. Apparent slow interchange with other carbinols was the result of lower initial concentration of these alcohols.

Aluminum diethyl methyl carbinoloxide and aluminum triethyl carbinoloxide, prepared for the first time, like their tert.-butoxide and tert.-amylxide homologues, could be sublimed.

To arrive at some interesting conclusions regarding the role of steric hindrance in alcohol interchange aluminum tert.-butoxide, which like aluminum mono-isopropoxide di-tert.-butoxide is also a dimer, was used as the starting material for the preparation of higher alkoxides. The method was successful and interchange was rapid and complete. If the steric hindrance argument holds, any interchange should cease at a composition of one tert.-butoxide group per aluminum atom ; instead pure compounds were prepared using relatively small starting quantities of

the higher alcohols. The latter method proved a more commendable one for the preparation of higher alkoxides of aluminum.

The preparation of mixed tert.alkoxides may need a brief comment. It is least practicable to start with aluminum isopropoxide, for the interchange reaction does not stop at a mono-isopropoxide di-tert.-alkoxide composition as suggested by earlier workers^{3,4}. Moreover it is essential to use a large excess of the higher alcohol for interchange to be reasonably rapid. Therefore it is better to start with the tert.-alkoxide and add the lower alcohol under control to get the desired mixed alkoxide of aluminum. It is possible to realize the even distribution of the isopropoxide groups in the product, if the conditions mentioned in the experimental section are observed.

The alkoxides and the mixed alkoxides reported in this paper progressively become less crystalline and more gluey and sticky. They crystallize on standing over long periods of time. The mixed alkoxides appear more crystalline than their corresponding higher alkoxides, probably because of a difference in their degrees of association. They also become less volatile with increasing molecular weight.

Molecular Weights :

It is apparent from table 2, that molecular complexity is decreasing with increasing bulk of the

alkoxide group ; it is lower in toluene than in benzene, showing, perhaps the effect of temperature on molecular weight. The bulky alkyl groups seem to cause greater back-coordination on account of the +I inductive effect, which renders the coordinate bonds weaker. Moreover, under ebullioscopic conditions, the coordinate bonds may disengage by thermal energy (agitation) to be reformed more slowly ; this may add up to the incidence of breaking the second bond, leading to monomerization.

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